

On McShane integrals of interval-valued functions and fuzzy-number-valued functions on Time Scales

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Abstract. In 2016, Hamid et al. [1] introduced the thought of the AP -Henstock integrals of interval-valued functions and fuzzy-number-valued functions and obtained a number of their properties. The aim of this paper is to introduce the thought of the McShane delta integrals of interval-valued functions and fuzzy-number-valued functions and discuss some of their properties.

Keywords: Fuzzy numbers; McShane delta integral of interval-valued functions; McShane delta integral of fuzzy-number-valued functions.

1 Introduction

The calculus on time scales was introduced for the first time in 1988 by Hilger [2] to unify the theory of difference equations and the theory of differential equations. The Henstock delta integral on time scales was introduced by Allan Peterson and Bevan Thompson [3] in 2006. In 2016, Hamid and Elmuiz [4] introduced the concept of the Henstock-Stieltjes (HS) integrals of interval-valued functions and fuzzy-number-valued functions and discussed a number of their properties.

In this paper, we introduce the notion of the McShane delta integrals of interval-valued functions and fuzzynumber-valued functions and investigate some of their properties.

The paper is organized as follows, in Section 2 we have a tendency to provide the preliminary terminology used in this paper. Section 3 is dedicated to discussing the McShane delta integral of interval-valued functions. In Section 4, we present the McShane delta integral of fuzzy-number-valued functions. The last section provides Conclusions.

2 Preliminaries

A time scale $\mathbf{T}$ is a nonempty closed subset of real number $\mathbb{R}$ with the subspace topology inherited from the standard topology of $\mathbb{R}$. For $t \in \mathbf{T}$ we define the forward jump operator $\sigma(t) = \inf\{s \in \mathbf{T} : s > t\}$ where $\inf \phi = \sup\{\mathbf{T}\}$, while the backward jump operator $\rho(t) = \sup\{s \in \mathbf{T} : s < t\}$ where $\sup \phi = \inf\{\mathbf{T}\}$. If $\sigma(t) > t$, we say that t is right-scattered, while if $\rho(t) < t$, we say that t is left-scattered. If $\sigma(t) = t$, we say that t is right-dense, while if $\rho(t) = t$, we say that t is left-dense. The forward graininess function $\mu(t)$ of $t \in \mathbf{T}$ is defined by $\mu(t) = \sigma(t) - t$, while the backward graininess function $\nu(t)$ of $t \in \mathbf{T}$ is defined by $\nu(t) = t - \rho(t)$. For $a, b \in \mathbf{T}$ we denote the closed interval $[a, b]_{\mathbf{T}} = \{t \in \mathbf{T} : a \leq t \leq b\}$.

Throughout this paper, all considered intervals will be intervals in $\mathbf{T}$. A division P of $[a, b]_{\mathbf{T}}$ is a finite collection of interval-point pairs $\{([t_{i-1}, t_i]_{\mathbf{T}}; \xi_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, where $\{a = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{n-1} < t_n = b\}$ and $\xi_i \in [a, b]_{\mathbf{T}}$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. By $\Delta t_i = t_i - t_{i-1}$ we denote the length of i th subinterval in the division P . $\delta(\xi) = (\delta_L(\xi), \delta_R(\xi))$ is a Δ -gauge for $[a, b]_{\mathbf{T}}$ provided $\delta_L(\xi) > 0$ on $(a, b]_{\mathbf{T}}$, $\delta_R(\xi) > 0$ on $[a, b)_{\mathbf{T}}$, $\delta_L(a) \geq 0$, $\delta_R(b) \geq 0$ and $\delta_R(b) \geq \mu(\xi)$

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for all $\xi \in [a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. We say that $P = \{([t_{i-1}, t_i]_{\mathbb{T}}; \xi_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ is a δ -fine McShane division of $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ if $[t_{i-1}, t_i]_{\mathbb{T}} \subset (\xi_i - \delta_L(\xi_i), \xi_i + \delta_R(\xi_i))_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $\xi_i \in [a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Definition 2.1 [5] A real-valued function $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be McShane (M) integrable to B on $[a, b]$ if for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there is a function $\delta(t) > 0$ such that for any δ -fine McShane division $P = \{([u_i, v_i]; \xi_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ of $[a, b]$, we have

$$\left| \sum_{i=1}^n f(\xi_i)(v_i - u_i) - B \right| < \varepsilon, \tag{2.1}$$

we write $(M) \int_a^b f(t) dt = B$, and $f \in M[a, b]$.

Definition 2.2 [6] A function $f : [a, b]_{\mathbb{T}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is McShane delta integrable (McShane Δ -integrable) on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ if there exists a number $A \in \mathbb{R}$ such that for each $\varepsilon > 0$ there is a Δ -gauge, δ , on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ such that

$$\left| \sum_{i=1}^n f(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}) - A \right| < \varepsilon \tag{2.2}$$

for each δ -fine McShane division $P = \{([t_{i-1}, t_i]_{\mathbb{T}}; \xi_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ of $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. A is called McShane Δ -integral of f on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, and we write $A = (M) \int_a^b f(t) \Delta t$.

Theorem 2.1 If $f(t)$ and $g(t)$ are McShane Δ -integrable on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $f(t) \leq g(t)$ almost everywhere on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then

$$(M) \int_a^b f(t) \Delta t \leq (M) \int_a^b g(t) \Delta t. \tag{2.3}$$

Proof The proof follows easily from the same argument in Theorem 3.6 [5]. □

3 McShane delta integral of interval-valued functions on time scales

In this section, we introduce the notion of the McShane delta integral of interval-valued functions on time scales and investigate some of their properties.

Definition 3.1 [7] Let $I_{\mathbb{R}} = \{I = [I^-, I^+] : I \text{ is the closed bounded interval on the real line } \mathbb{R}\}$.

For $A, B \in I_{\mathbb{R}}$, we define $A \leq B$ iff $A^- \leq B^-$ and $A^+ \leq B^+$, $A+B = C$ iff $C^- = A^- + B^-$ and $C^+ = A^+ + B^+$, and $A \cdot B = \{a \cdot b : a \in A, b \in B\}$, where

$$(A \cdot B)^- = \min\{A^- \cdot B^-, A^- \cdot B^+, A^+ \cdot B^-, A^+ \cdot B^+\} \tag{3.1}$$

and

$$(A \cdot B)^+ = \max\{A^- \cdot B^-, A^- \cdot B^+, A^+ \cdot B^-, A^+ \cdot B^+\}. \tag{3.2}$$

Define $d(A, B) = \max(|A^- - B^-|, |A^+ - B^+|)$ as the distance between intervals A and B .

Definition 3.2 [8] Let $F : [a, b] \rightarrow I_{\mathbb{R}}$ be an interval-valued function. $I_0 \in I_{\mathbb{R}}$, for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there is a $\delta(t) > 0$ such that for any δ -fine McShane division $P = \{([u_i, v_i]; \xi_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, we have

$$d\left(\sum_{i=1}^n F(\xi_i)(v_i - u_i), I_0\right) < \varepsilon, \tag{3.3}$$

then $F(t)$ is said to be McShane integrable over $[a, b]$ and write $(IM) \int_a^b F(t) dt = I_0$. For brevity, we write $F(t) \in IM[a, b]$.

Definition 3.3 A interval-valued function $F : [a, b]_{\mathbb{T}} \rightarrow I_{\mathbb{R}}$ is McShane delta integrable to $I_0 \in I_{\mathbb{R}}$ on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a Δ -gauge, δ , on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ such that

$$d\left(\sum_{i=1}^n F(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}), I_0\right) < \varepsilon, \tag{3.4}$$

whenever $P = \{([t_{i-1}, t_i]_{\mathbb{T}}; \xi_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ is a δ -fine McShane division of $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. We write $(IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t = I_0$ and $F \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$.

Remark 3.1 If $F(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then the integral value is unique.

Theorem 3.1 An interval-valued function $F : [a, b]_{\mathbb{T}} \rightarrow I_{\mathbb{R}}$ is McShane delta integrable on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ if and only if $F^-, F^+ \in M[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$(IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t = \left[(M) \int_a^b F^-(t)\Delta t, (M) \int_a^b F^+(t)\Delta t \right]. \tag{3.5}$$

Proof Let $F \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then there exists an interval $I_0 = [I_0^-, I_0^+]$ with the property that for any $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a Δ -gauge, δ , on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ such that

$$d\left(\sum_{i=1}^n F(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}), I_0\right) < \varepsilon, \tag{3.6}$$

whenever $P = \{([t_{i-1}, t_i]_{\mathbb{T}}; \xi_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ is a δ -fine McShane division of $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$.

Since $t_i - t_{i-1} \geq 0$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & d\left(\sum_{i=1}^n F(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}), I_0\right) \\ &= \max\left(\left|\left[\sum_{i=1}^n F(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1})\right]^- - I_0^-\right|, \left|\left[\sum_{i=1}^n F(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1})\right]^+ - I_0^+\right|\right) < \varepsilon. \\ &= \max\left(\left|\sum_{i=1}^n F^-(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}) - I_0^-\right|, \left|\sum_{i=1}^n F^+(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}) - I_0^+\right|\right) < \varepsilon. \end{aligned} \tag{3.7}$$

Hence $\left|\sum_{i=1}^n F^-(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}) - I_0^-\right| < \varepsilon$, $\left|\sum_{i=1}^n F^+(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}) - I_0^+\right| < \varepsilon$ whenever $P = \{([t_{i-1}, t_i]_{\mathbb{T}}; \xi_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ is a δ -fine McShane division of $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. Thus $F^-, F^+ \in M[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$(IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t = \left[(M) \int_a^b F^-(t)\Delta t, (M) \int_a^b F^+(t)\Delta t \right]. \tag{3.8}$$

Conversely, let $F^-, F^+ \in M[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. Then there exists $M_1, M_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ with the property that given $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a Δ -gauge, δ , on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ such that

$$\left|\sum_{i=1}^n F^-(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}) - M_1\right| < \varepsilon, \quad \left|\sum_{i=1}^n F^+(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}) - M_2\right| < \varepsilon$$

whenever $P = \{([t_{i-1}, t_i]_{\mathbb{T}}; \xi_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ is a δ -fine McShane division of $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. We define $I_0 = [M_1, M_2]$, then if $P = \{([t_{i-1}, t_i]_{\mathbb{T}}; \xi_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ is a δ -fine McShane division of $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, we have

$$d\left(\sum_{i=1}^n F(\xi_i)(t_i - t_{i-1}), I_0\right) < \varepsilon. \tag{3.9}$$

Hence $F : [a, b]_{\mathbb{T}} \rightarrow I_{\mathbb{R}}$ is McShane delta integrable on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. □

Theorem 3.2 If $F(t), G(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $\beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}$. Then $[\beta F(t) + \gamma G(t)] \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$(IM) \int_a^b (\beta F(t) + \gamma G(t))\Delta t = \beta(IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t + \gamma(IM) \int_a^b G(t)\Delta t. \tag{3.10}$$

Proof If $F(t), G(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then $F^-(t), F^+(t), G^-(t), G^+(t) \in M[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ by Theorem 3.1. Hence $\beta F^-(t) + \gamma G^-(t), \beta F^+(t) + \gamma G^+(t), \beta F^-(t) + \gamma G^+(t), \beta F^+(t) + \gamma G^-(t) \in M[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$.

(1) If $\beta > 0$ and $\gamma > 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} (M) \int_a^b (\beta F(t) + \gamma G(t))^- \Delta t &= (M) \int_a^b (\beta F^-(t) + \gamma G^-(t)) \Delta t \\ &= \beta (M) \int_a^b F^-(t) \Delta t + \gamma (M) \int_a^b G^-(t) \Delta t \\ &= \beta \left((IM) \int_a^b F(t) \Delta t \right)^- + \gamma \left((IM) \int_a^b G(t) \Delta t \right)^- \\ &= \left(\beta (IM) \int_a^b F(t) \Delta t + \gamma (IM) \int_a^b G(t) \Delta t \right)^-. \end{aligned}$$

(2) If $\beta < 0$ and $\gamma < 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} (M) \int_a^b (\beta F(t) + \gamma G(t))^- \Delta t &= (M) \int_a^b (\beta F^+(t) + \gamma G^+(t)) \Delta t \\ &= \beta (M) \int_a^b F^+(t) \Delta t + \gamma (M) \int_a^b G^+(t) \Delta t \\ &= \beta \left((IM) \int_a^b F(t) \Delta t \right)^+ + \gamma \left((IM) \int_a^b G(t) \Delta t \right)^+ \\ &= \left(\beta (IM) \int_a^b F(t) \Delta t + \gamma (IM) \int_a^b G(t) \Delta t \right)^-. \end{aligned}$$

(3) If $\beta > 0$ and $\gamma < 0$, (or $\beta < 0$ and $\gamma > 0$), then

$$\begin{aligned} (M) \int_a^b (\beta F(t) + \gamma G(t))^- \Delta t &= (M) \int_a^b (\beta F^-(t) + \gamma G^+(t)) \Delta t \\ &= \beta (M) \int_a^b F^-(t) \Delta t + \gamma (M) \int_a^b G^+(t) \Delta t \\ &= \beta \left((IM) \int_a^b F(t) \Delta t \right)^- + \gamma \left((IM) \int_a^b G(t) \Delta t \right)^+ \\ &= \left(\beta (IM) \int_a^b F(t) \Delta t + \gamma (IM) \int_a^b G(t) \Delta t \right)^-. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, for four cases above we have

$$(M) \int_a^b (\beta F(t) + \gamma G(t))^+ \Delta t = \left(\beta (IM) \int_a^b F(t) \Delta t + \gamma (IM) \int_a^b G(t) \Delta t \right)^+. \tag{3.11}$$

Hence by Theorem 3.1 $\beta F(t) + \gamma G(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$(IM) \int_a^b (\beta F(t) + \gamma G(t)) \Delta t = \beta (IM) \int_a^b F(t) \Delta t + \gamma (IM) \int_a^b G(t) \Delta t. \tag{3.12}$$

□

Theorem 3.3 If $F(t) \in IM[a, c]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $F(t) \in IM[c, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then $F(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$(IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t = (IM) \int_a^c F(t)\Delta t + (IM) \int_c^b F(t)\Delta t. \tag{3.13}$$

Proof If $F(t) \in IM[a, c]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $F(t) \in IM[c, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then by Theorem 3.1 $F^-(t), F^+(t) \in M[a, c]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $F^-(t), F^+(t) \in M[c, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. Hence $F^-(t), F^+(t) \in M[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} (M) \int_a^b F^-(t)\Delta t &= (M) \int_a^c F^-(t)\Delta t + (M) \int_c^b F^-(t)\Delta t \\ &= \left((IM) \int_a^c F(t)\Delta t + (IM) \int_c^b F(t)\Delta t \right)^-. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $(M) \int_a^b F^+(t)\Delta t = \left((IM) \int_a^c F(t)\Delta t + (IM) \int_c^b F(t)\Delta t \right)^+$. Hence by Theorem 3.1 $F(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$(IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t = (IM) \int_a^c F(t)\Delta t + (IM) \int_c^b F(t)\Delta t. \tag{3.14}$$

□

Theorem 3.4 If $F(t) \leq G(t)$ nearly everywhere on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $F(t), G(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then

$$(IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t \leq (IM) \int_a^b G(t)\Delta t. \tag{3.15}$$

Proof Let $F(t) \leq G(t)$ nearly everywhere on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $F(t), G(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. Then $F^-(t), F^+(t), G^-(t), G^+(t) \in M[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $F^-(t) \leq G^-(t), F^+(t) \leq G^+(t)$ nearly everywhere on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. By Theorem 2.1 $(M) \int_a^b F^-(t)\Delta t \leq (M) \int_a^b G^-(t)\Delta t$ and $(M) \int_a^b F^+(t)\Delta t \leq (M) \int_a^b G^+(t)\Delta t$. Hence

$$(IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t \leq (IM) \int_a^b G(t)\Delta t, \tag{3.16}$$

by Theorem 3.1.

□

Theorem 3.5 Let $F(t), G(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $d(F(t), G(t))$ is Lebesgue integrable on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. Then

$$d\left((IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t, (IM) \int_a^b G(t)\Delta t \right) \leq (L) \int_a^b d(F(t), G(t))\Delta t. \tag{3.17}$$

Proof By definition of distance,

$$\begin{aligned} &d\left((IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t, (IM) \int_a^b G(t)\Delta t \right) \\ &= \max \left(\left| \left((IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t \right)^- - \left((IM) \int_a^b G(t)\Delta t \right)^- \right|, \left| \left((IM) \int_a^b F(t)\Delta t \right)^+ - \left((IM) \int_a^b G(t)\Delta t \right)^+ \right| \right) \\ &= \max \left(\left| (M) \int_a^b (F^-(t) - G^-(t))\Delta t \right|, \left| (M) \int_a^b (F^+(t) - G^+(t))\Delta t \right| \right) \\ &\leq \max \left((L) \int_a^b |F^-(t) - G^-(t)|\Delta t, (L) \int_a^b |F^+(t) - G^+(t)|\Delta t \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq (L) \int_a^b \max \left(\left| F^-(t) - G^-(t) \right| \Delta t, \left| F^+(t) - G^+(t) \right| \Delta t \right) \\ &= (L) \int_a^b d(F(t), G(t)). \end{aligned} \tag{3.18}$$

□

4 McShane delta integral of fuzzy-number-valued functions on time scales

This section introduces the notion of the McShane delta integral of fuzzy-number-valued functions and discusses some of their properties.

Definition 4.1 [9, 10, 11] Let $\tilde{A} \in F(\mathbb{R})$ be a fuzzy subset on $\mathbb{R}$. If for any $\lambda \in [0, 1]$, $A_\lambda = [A_\lambda^-, A_\lambda^+]$ and $A_\lambda \neq \emptyset$, where $A_\lambda = \{t : \tilde{A}(t) \geq \lambda\}$, then $\tilde{A}$ is called a fuzzy number. If $\tilde{A}$ is (1) convex, (2) normal, (3) upper semi-continuous, (4) has the compact support, we say that $\tilde{A}$ is a compact fuzzy number.

Let $\tilde{\mathbb{R}}$ denote the set of all fuzzy numbers.

Definition 4.2 [9] Let $\tilde{A}, \tilde{B} \in \tilde{\mathbb{R}}$, we define (1) $\tilde{A} \leq \tilde{B}$ iff $A_\lambda \leq B_\lambda$ for all $\lambda \in (0, 1]$, (2) $\tilde{A} + \tilde{B} = \tilde{C}$ iff $A_\lambda + B_\lambda = C_\lambda$ for any $\lambda \in (0, 1]$, (3) $\tilde{A} \cdot \tilde{B} = \tilde{D}$ iff $A_\lambda \cdot B_\lambda = D_\lambda$ for any $\lambda \in (0, 1]$.

For $\tilde{A}, \tilde{B} \in \tilde{\mathbb{R}}^C$, then

$$D(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}) = \sup_{\lambda \in [0, 1]} d(A_\lambda, B_\lambda), \tag{4.1}$$

is called the distance between $\tilde{A}$ and $\tilde{B}$.

Lemma 4.1 [12] If a mapping $H : [0, 1] \rightarrow I_{\mathbb{R}}$, $\lambda \rightarrow H(\lambda) = [m_\lambda, n_\lambda]$, satisfies $[m_{\lambda_1}, n_{\lambda_1}] \supset [m_{\lambda_2}, n_{\lambda_2}]$ when $\lambda_1 < \lambda_2$, then

$$\tilde{A} := \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0, 1]} \lambda H(\lambda) \in \tilde{\mathbb{R}} \tag{4.2}$$

and

$$A_\lambda = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} H(\lambda_n), \tag{4.3}$$

where $\lambda_n = [1 - \frac{1}{(n+1)}]\lambda$.

Definition 4.3 Let $\tilde{F} : [a, b]_{\mathbb{T}} \rightarrow \tilde{\mathbb{R}}$. If the interval-valued function $F_\lambda(t) = [F_\lambda^-(t), F_\lambda^+(t)]$ is McShane delta integrable on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ for any $\lambda \in (0, 1]$, then $\tilde{F}(t)$ is called McShane delta integrable on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and the integral is defined by McShane delta integral is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} (FM) \int_a^b \tilde{F}(t) \Delta t &:= \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0, 1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a^b F_\lambda(t) \Delta t \\ &= \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0, 1]} \lambda \left[(M) \int_a^b F_\lambda^-(t) \Delta t, (M) \int_a^b F_\lambda^+(t) \Delta t \right]. \end{aligned}$$

We write $\tilde{F}(t) \in FM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$.

Theorem 4.1 $\tilde{F}(t) \in FM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then $(FM) \int_a^b \tilde{F}(t) \Delta t \in \tilde{\mathbb{R}}$ and

$$\left[(FM) \int_a^b \tilde{F}(t) \Delta t \right]_\lambda = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} (IM) \int_a^b F_{\lambda_n}(t) \Delta t, \tag{4.4}$$

where $\lambda_n = [1 - \frac{1}{(n+1)}]\lambda$.

Proof Let $H : (0, 1] \rightarrow I_{\mathbb{R}}$, be defined by $H(\lambda) = [(M) \int_a F_{\lambda}^{-}(t)\Delta t, (M) \int_a F_{\lambda}^{+}(t)\Delta t]$.

Since $F_{\lambda}^{-}(t)$ and $F_{\lambda}^{+}(t)$ are increasing and decreasing on λ respectively, therefore, when $0 < \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq 1$, we have $F_{\lambda_1}^{-}(t) \leq F_{\lambda_2}^{-}(t)$, $F_{\lambda_1}^{+}(t) \geq F_{\lambda_2}^{+}(t)$, on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$. From Theorem 3.4 we have

$$\left[(M) \int_a F_{\lambda_1}^{-}(t)\Delta t, (M) \int_a F_{\lambda_1}^{+}(t)\Delta t \right] \supset \left[(M) \int_a F_{\lambda_2}^{-}(t)\Delta t, (M) \int_a F_{\lambda_2}^{+}(t)\Delta t \right]. \quad (4.5)$$

Using Theorem 3.1 and Lemma 4.1 we obtain

$$(FM) \int_a \tilde{F}(t)\Delta t := \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda \left[(M) \int_a F_{\lambda}^{-}(t)\Delta t, (M) \int_a F_{\lambda}^{+}(t)\Delta t \right] \in \tilde{\mathbb{R}} \quad (4.6)$$

and for all $\lambda \in (0, 1]$,

$$[(FM) \int_a \tilde{F}(t)\Delta t]_{\lambda} = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} (IM) \int_a F_{\lambda_n}(t)\Delta t, \quad (4.7)$$

where $\lambda_n = [1 - \frac{1}{(n+1)}]\lambda$. □

Theorem 4.2 If $\tilde{F}(t), \tilde{G}(t) \in FM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $\beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}$. Then $\beta\tilde{F}(t) + \gamma\tilde{G}(t) \in FM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$(FM) \int_a (\beta\tilde{F}(t) + \gamma\tilde{G}(t))\Delta t = \beta(FM) \int_a \tilde{F}(t)\Delta t + \gamma(FM) \int_a \tilde{G}(t)\Delta t. \quad (4.8)$$

Proof If $\tilde{F}(t), \tilde{G}(t) \in FM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then the interval-valued function $F_{\lambda}(t) = [F_{\lambda}^{-}(t), F_{\lambda}^{+}(t)]$ and $G_{\lambda}(t) = [G_{\lambda}^{-}(t), G_{\lambda}^{+}(t)]$ are McShane delta integrable on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ for any $\lambda \in (0, 1]$ and $(FM) \int_a \tilde{F}(t)\Delta t = \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a F_{\lambda}(t)\Delta t$

and $(FM) \int_a \tilde{G}(t)\Delta t = \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a G_{\lambda}(t)\Delta t$. From Theorem 3.2 we have $\beta F_{\lambda}(t) + \gamma G_{\lambda}(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $(IM) \int_a (\beta F_{\lambda}(t) + \gamma G_{\lambda}(t))\Delta t = \beta (IM) \int_a F_{\lambda}(t)\Delta t + \gamma (IM) \int_a G_{\lambda}(t)\Delta t$ for any $\lambda \in (0, 1]$. Hence $\beta\tilde{F}(t) + \gamma\tilde{G}(t) \in FM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} (FM) \int_a (\beta\tilde{F}(t) + \gamma\tilde{G}(t))\Delta t &= \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a (\beta F_{\lambda}(t) + \gamma G_{\lambda}(t))\Delta t \\ &= \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda \left(\beta (IM) \int_a F_{\lambda}(t)\Delta t + \gamma (IM) \int_a G_{\lambda}(t)\Delta t \right) \\ &= \beta \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a F_{\lambda}(t)\Delta t + \gamma \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a G_{\lambda}(t)\Delta t \\ &= \beta (FM) \int_a \tilde{F}(t)\Delta t + \gamma (FM) \int_a \tilde{G}(t)\Delta t. \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 4.3 If $\tilde{F}(t) \in FM[a, c]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $\tilde{F}(t) \in FM[c, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then $\tilde{F}(t) \in FM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$(FM) \int_a \tilde{F}(t)\Delta t = (FM) \int_a \tilde{F}(t)\Delta t + (FM) \int_c \tilde{F}(t)\Delta t. \quad (4.9)$$

Proof If $\tilde{F}(t) \in FM[a, c]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $\tilde{F}(t) \in FM[c, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then the interval-valued function $F_{\lambda}(t) = [F_{\lambda}^{-}(t), F_{\lambda}^{+}(t)]$ is McShane delta integrable on $[a, c]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $[c, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ for any $\lambda \in (0, 1]$ and $(FM) \int_a \tilde{F}(t)\Delta t = \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a F_{\lambda}(t)\Delta t$ and

$(FM) \int_c^b \tilde{F}(t) \Delta t = \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_c^b F_\lambda(t) \Delta t$. From Theorem 3.3 we have $F_\lambda(t) \in IM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $(IM) \int_a^b F_\lambda(t) \Delta t = (IM) \int_a^c F_\lambda(t) \Delta t + (IM) \int_c^b F_\lambda(t) \Delta t$ for any $\lambda \in (0, 1]$. Hence $\tilde{F}(t) \in FM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} (FM) \int_a^b \tilde{F}(t) \Delta t &= \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a^b F_\lambda(t) \Delta t \\ &= \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda \left((IM) \int_a^c F_\lambda(t) \Delta t + (IM) \int_c^b F_\lambda(t) \Delta t \right) \\ &= \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a^c F_\lambda(t) \Delta t + \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_c^b F_\lambda(t) \Delta t \\ &= (FM) \int_a^c \tilde{F}(t) \Delta t + (FM) \int_c^b \tilde{F}(t) \Delta t. \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 4.4 If $\tilde{F}(t) \leq \tilde{G}(t)$ nearly everywhere on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $\tilde{F}(t), \tilde{G}(t) \in FM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then

$$(FM) \int_a^b \tilde{F}(t) \Delta t \leq (FM) \int_a^b \tilde{G}(t) \Delta t. \tag{4.10}$$

Proof If $\tilde{F}(t) \leq \tilde{G}(t)$ nearly everywhere on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ and $\tilde{F}(t), \tilde{G}(t) \in FM[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$, then $F_\lambda(t) \leq G_\lambda(t)$ nearly everywhere on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ for any $\lambda \in (0, 1]$ and $F_\lambda(t)$ and $G_\lambda(t)$ are McShane delta integrable on $[a, b]_{\mathbb{T}}$ for any $\lambda \in (0, 1]$ and $(FM) \int_a^b \tilde{F}(t) \Delta t = \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a^b F_\lambda(t) \Delta t$ and $(FM) \int_a^b \tilde{G}(t) \Delta t = \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a^b G_\lambda(t) \Delta t$. From Theorem 3.4 we have $(IM) \int_a^b F_\lambda(t) \Delta t \leq (IM) \int_a^b G_\lambda(t) \Delta t$ for any $\lambda \in (0, 1]$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (FM) \int_a^b \tilde{F}(t) \Delta t &= \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a^b F_\lambda(t) \Delta t \\ &\leq \bigcup_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \lambda (IM) \int_a^b G_\lambda(t) \Delta t \\ &= (FM) \int_a^b \tilde{G}(t) \Delta t. \end{aligned}$$

□

5 conclusions

In this paper, we have a tendency to introduced the concept of the McShane delta integrals of interval-valued functions and fuzzy number- valued functions and discussed some properties of those integrals.

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